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ON THE PRESENCE OF MILLIPEDE *OXIDUS GRACILIS*
(*Diplopoda Polydesmida Paradoxosomatidae*) IN SICILY

SUMMARY

Oxidus gracilis is a rapidly spreading alien species in the Mediterranean area, when it usually occupies humid environments in anthropized and rural contexts. Its presence in Sicily is made official.

Key words. Alien species, *Oxidus gracilis*, Sicily.

RIASSUNTO

Sulla presenza del millepiedi Oxidus gracilis in Sicilia (Diplopoda Polydesmida Paradoxosomatidae). *Oxidus gracilis* è una specie aliena in rapida diffusione nell'area mediterranea, dove solitamente occupa ambienti umidi in contesti antropizzati e rurali. Viene ufficializzata la sua presenza in Sicilia.

Parole chiave. Specie aliena, *Oxidus gracilis*, Sicilia.

INTRODUCTION

Diplopods are usually small (they range in size from as little as 2 mm to 30 cm in length), the vast majority of them are, soil-dwelling detritivorous arthropods, characterized by having two pairs of legs on most body segments. Although most of them are hygrophilous. They have managed to colonize different habitats, including extreme environments such as deserts and high mountains (ADIS, 2002; DAVID, 2015). Climatic conditions, soil type, presence of predators, food availability and biocenosis are ecological factors that can influence the presence or absence of diplopods in a given geographical area (KICAJ, 2023).

Oxidus gracilis (Koch, 1847), known as the ‘greenhouse millipede’, is a cosmopolitan species (JEEKEL, 1968), probably native to East Asia (NGUYEN *et al.*, 2017). The species is widely distributed over the world, mainly in warm temperate regions, and associated with disturbed habitats. Records of *O. gracilis* in hothouses or greenhouses, associated with imported plants from the Holarctic (BLOWER, 1985; DAVID, 2015), suggest a distribution highly correlated to commercial activities (INIESTA *et al.*, 2020). *Oxidus gracilis* has been reported from Europe: free-living or confined to greenhouses (BLOWER, 1985; MIKHALJOVA, 2004) and in different maritime regions: the West Indies and islands in the Atlantic and Pacific (NGUYEN & SIERWALD, 2013; NGUYEN *et al.*, 2017). The species is widespread throughout the tropics, occurring in forests, urban and rural areas (GOLOVATCH & KIME, 2009).

Although it has been reported in continental and peninsular Italy (FODDAI *et al.*, 1995; Zapparoli in FIACCHINI *et al.*, 2008; STOEV *et al.*, 2010; DRAGO *et al.*, 2011; MINELLI in Bologna, 2021), and in Sardinia, in cave environments (STRASSER, 1974) and in the nearby island of Malta by ENGHOFF & SCHEMBRI (1989), its presence in Sicily is known only from a geographical report in KIME & ENGHOFF (2011), but subsequently it has not been further confirmed or made official with a more scientific note, despite recent reports and photographs found on the Web.

STUDY AREA

The study area mainly includes the western sector of Sicily. The surveyed places have common microclimatic conditions and habitats. The sectors of the Botanical Garden of Palermo and the gardens in Viale delle Scienze are mostly in half-light with trees and shrubs, covering litter and boulders. In Monreale the place of discovery is a garden with the same environmental conditions. The same is true for the place of discovery in Mazara del Vallo. Only Colle Atollo appears to be the most differentiated study area since it involves the underground environment, but like the previous ones it maintains almost constant temperature and humidity. The online reports come from rural or peripheral city sites.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Specimens were searched in the field exclusively by sight, lifting rocks, wood, rummaging through foliage, moving the surface layer of soil with abundant organic matter. Collection is random, based on the number of specimens without numerically damaging the observed population. First they were placed in con-

tainers for transport to the laboratory. In the laboratory, fixation is carried out in 75-80% alcohol or, with larger samplings, an initial exposure to -18° for less invasive killing. After 1 hour, they are exposed again to room temperature and rinsed thoroughly in running or demineralized water on 55 mm and 75 mm diameter petri dishes. Subsequently, they are placed in 75-80% alcohol in test tubes of various capacities based on the number of specimens (from 1.5 ml to 5 ml). The gonopods were photographed directly on the specimen without extracting them. The examined material is currently preserved in Viviano Collection (Palermo).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Order Polydesmida Leach, 1815; Family Paradoxosomatidae Daday, 1889

Oxidus gracilis (Koch, 1847)

Examined material. Palermo, San Giovanni Apostolo, Colle Atollo, grotte, 7.II.2016, $38^{\circ}08'17''\text{N } 13^{\circ}18'13''\text{E}$, 95 m (2 ex), legit R. Viviano; Palermo, Orto Botanico, Viale Vincenzo Tineo, under vase, 10.V.2022, legit R. Viviano; idem, Palmetum, near *Searsia pendulina*, 02.V.2024 (14 ex), legit R. Viviano; idem, same sector, 22.VII.2024 (10 ex), legit R. Viviano; Palermo, Viale delle Scienze, Engineering Dept., 19.VII.2024, $38^{\circ}06'16.5''\text{N } 13^{\circ}20'49.4''\text{E}$ (1 ex), legit R. Viviano; **Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)**, private garden, 14.V.2021 (2 ex), legit A. Ditta; **Monreale (PA)**, Caculla, 5.XI.2023, $38^{\circ}02'47.7''\text{N } 13^{\circ}14'45.7''\text{E}$, legit A. Dentici.

Online material. Facebook (Fauna Siciliana group): Mazara del Vallo (1 ex) (Ditta, 31.XII.2020); Palermo (1 ex) (Compagno, 25.IX.2023); **Forum Entomologi Italiani**: Modica (Ragusa) (2 ex) on *Ortensia* litter (Risoldi, III.2009); **INaturalist**: Palermo (1 ex) ("Matteot", 7.V.2020); Milazzo (Messina), Olivarella-Corriolo (2 ex) (De Mariano, 14.VI.2022); idem, in urbe (1 ex) (Allegra, 4.X.2022); idem, Contrada Bilemi (2 ex) (Schittone e Torre, 28.IV.2023); idem, Contrada Filicusa, 1 ex (Scibilia, 4.V.2023).

Ecological notes

Oxidus gracilis has proven to be a species very adaptable to different environmental contexts, but with the close presence of man. This further strengthens its passive introduction by man, through the transport of plants probably bought in nurseries and specialized companies and subsequently planted. The animal also seems to have adapted well to our temperatures and weather-climate conditions. In the places where it was found, massive populations have not been observed, but only nuclei contained in small areas,

never exceeding twenty specimens; for example, at the Botanical Garden of Palermo, its presence has been found in a few points compared to the entire area. In other places mentioned above, the populations appear to be point-like and composed of a few units and/or more or less numerous cores.

The places where *Oxidus gracilis* has been found almost entirely share many of the conditions that allow this species to live: temperature, humidity and shelter. In Botanical Garden of Palermo, where the largest population has been found so far, both in summer and winter, cooler temperatures and constant humidity are generally maintained thanks to frequent watering. In Viale delle Scienze, a single specimen was found dead inside a structure, adjacent to an outdoor garden, in a shaded and generally humid area. In Mazara del Vallo, *Oxidus gracilis* has managed to form a stable population inside a private garden. In the Monreale area, only a few specimens have been found in the soil of a potted plant purchased in a shop, but kept outside the home near a garden, which is why it is difficult to establish whether it was already present in the pot, the more likely hypothesis, or whether it arrived there directly from the garden. In San Giovanni Apostolo district of Palermo, found inside the Colle Atollo caves, the specimens were found on the out-cropping rocks wet by dripping water; outside the hypogeum context, a rural environment with a sheepfold and houses nearby is found. The locations of the online reports also reflect the previous ones, excluding the cave.

Systematic notes

The most studied population is that of the Botanical Garden of Palermo (Fig. 1A). In this locality, it finds refuge especially under the rocks and in the litter (especially in the juvenile stage). In brevis, it is distinguished from the genus *Stosatea* Gray, 1843, present in Sicily as a native species, by a larger size, wider tergites and flattened and angled paranota on the lower margin, shiny dark brown color with yellowish margins, and by the absence of yellow-orange spots on the tergites (present on *Stosatea italica* (Latzel, 1886)). Adults show a slight sexual dimorphism where the most evident difference is in size: females measure a length of 22 mm, while males measure a length of 18 mm (Fig. 1B). Binocular observation of adult males has allowed a greater ascertainment of the species with the study of the gonopods, visible in Figs. 1C, D, which are distinguished from *Stosatea* not only by the larger size of the gonopods, but also by the more complex articulation of the gonopodial apex. It was possible to observe, even if only partially, the biological cycle of this species: in the winter months (February) only young, pale yellowish colored animals were found under rocks. In spring-summer, from May to July, adult specimens can be observed, some of which are fresh from moulting (especially in spring)

Fig. 1 — *Oxidus gracilis* (Koch, 1847). A: adult specimen photographed under a stone at the Botanical Garden of Palermo; B: two specimens of different sexes from the same locality in dorsal view to show their dimorphism, male on the left, female on the right; C, D: male gonopods, in dorsal and lateral view respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

Oxidus gracilis is one of the many alien species that have successfully established themselves in Sicily. Considering that it is an alien species, the authors believe it is appropriate to monitor this species in the already known populations and to records further ones for any future studies, possibly focused on ecology. The monitoring would be useful in the case of population increase and on the interactions of this species with others present in the same environments, as for example *Stosatea italica* (Polydesmida Paradoxosomatidae), *Brachydesmus proximus* Latzel, 1889 (Polydesmida Polydesmidae), *Ommatoiulus oxypygus* Brandt, 1841 (Julida Julidae) and *Pachyiulus flavipes* (Koch, 1837) (Julida Julidae), have not yet led to unfavorable conditions such as the replacement of native species.

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